

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF BASIC EDUCATION LEARNING CONTINUITY PLAN (BE-LCP) OF GAMU DISTRICT: ITS OPPORTUNITIES, CHALLENGES, AND EFFECT ON SCHOOL PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic significantly disrupted education in the Philippines, prompting the Department of Education (DepEd) to implement the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) to ensure uninterrupted learning. This study examines the assessment of elementary and secondary school heads and teachers in the Gamu District regarding the implementation of the BE-LCP, focusing on the opportunities, challenges, and its impact on school performance. Key areas of the BE-LCP include curriculum support, modular distance learning, health protocols, capacity building, and stakeholder engagement. The study revealed that while BE-LCP provided significant opportunities, particularly in delivering flexible learning options and enhancing stakeholder collaboration, it also posed challenges. These include difficulty in independent learning for some students, the production of learning materials, and limited student-teacher interaction, which affected learning outcomes. Furthermore, elementary and secondary teachers had differing perceptions of BE-LCP's implementation, with elementary teachers viewing governance and operations as more challenging, while secondary teachers perceived more challenges in modular learning and health protocols. Despite these challenges, both school levels showed improvement in enrolment and dropout rates. However, completion rates in elementary schools saw a decline. The findings suggest that while the BE-LCP contributed to maintaining education access, further adjustments are needed to address ongoing challenges and improve learning outcomes, especially in elementary schools. The study recommends sustained implementation, teacher reskilling, and continuous monitoring to ensure quality education in future crises.

Keywords: *Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BELCP), School Performance*

INTRODUCTION

In an institution there are programmed and non-programmed decisions that need to be undertaken when faced with issues and problems. With the coming of the covid-19 in the Philippines that had greatly affected its education system, the Department of Education had to do something so that its business in education would not be compromised by the virus. What the Department had to do, its adjustments in the curriculum, adoption of other learning delivery modalities, reskilling of its manpower, implementation of health protocols, and many other more, are classic example of non-programmed decisions. This is so because nobody has never been in this situation, not even the Education Secretary herself.

There is nobody that has never been touched by the covid-19 pandemic. It has left no country unscathed. The Philippines, like other countries, and its education system were not spared. The presence of the said virus in the country led to the closure of many educational institutions and universities. This, in turn, affected learning opportunities especially those involving in-person interactions. Numerous governments in the entire globe, that includes the Philippines, decided to temporarily close schools in order to reduce the spread of covid-19.

By virtue of the Proclamation No. 929 series of 20201 by the President of the Philippines Declaring a State of Calamity Throughout the Philippines Due to the Corona Virus Disease 2019 and the Memorandum From the Executive Secretary of the Office of the President dated March 16, 2020 regarding Community Quarantine Over the Entire Luzon and Further Guidelines for the Management of the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) Situation, Enhanced Community Quarantine throughout Luzon beginning 12 midnight (March 17, 2020) until April 12, 2020 was imposed, therefore suspending classes and all school activities in all levels until April 14, 2020 and shall resume on April 15, 2020. However, the virus was not contained that soon. As the country continues to confront different issues brought about by the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, the Department of Education (DepEd) addressed the challenges in the basic education for the school year 2020-2021 through its Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) under DepEd Order No. 012, s. 2020. The BE-LCP is consistent with the mandate of Section 1, Article XIV of the 1987 Constitution for the state to protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels, and to take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all. Under Section 6, Chapter 1 of Republic Act No. 9155, or the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, DepEd is vested with the authority, accountability, and responsibility for ensuring access to, promoting equity in, and improving the quality of basic education.⁴ The BE-LCP aims to ensure the health, safety, and well-being of the learners, teachers, and personnel in the time of covid-19, while finding ways for education to continue amidst the crisis. In particular, the BE-LCP has been designed with a legal framework responsive to the "new normal," keeping in

mind the constitutional mandate to uphold the right of all citizens to quality education at all times.

As the implementation of the BE-LCP prioritizes learning and the continuity of the provision of access, quality and liberating education under the new normal of Basic Education due to the covid-19 threat it is seen to offer opportunities in the development of comprehensive plan on the continuity of learning through flexible learning delivery options using different modalities with emphasis on distant learning as well as to effectively and efficiently deliver essential learning competencies to ensure quality education.

Teachers and other school personnel capability programs through online trainings, prioritizing on the protection and promotion of mental health and general welfare of all learners and personnel, engagement of external stakeholders for support and collaboration, provision of technical assistance to the schools to quality assure, monitor and evaluate programs, and maximizing the use of various online platforms in the dissemination of information, issues and concerns are as well seen to be opportunities as the BE-LCP is applied.

However, in its implementation, the BE-LCP is confronted with different challenges. DepEd and schools will need substantial and additional financial resources in order to meet the objectives of the BE-LCP.

In the implementation of the various learning delivery modalities, the challenge will be in dealing with learners under any of the modes of distance learning or blended learning who are not capable of learning independently, or who are not periodically supported by their parents or guardians. Also critical for the implementation will be the mass production of the needed teachers and learners' learning materials.

The holistic development of students will likely be affected. With the BE-LCP in place, the students will have limited opportunities for interaction with their teachers and classmates. Thus, their learning outcomes may be affected, and there may be negative impacts on the students who cannot easily cope with the change.

Verily, the learning environment amidst the COVID-19 pandemic will be very different. DepEd is optimistic that despite the situation, the implementation of the BE-LCP will still be beneficial. Notwithstanding the various socio-economic situations of families which affect the provision of learning support in the home, and the peculiar needs of different learners, the BE-LCP could be the key to providing quality basic education which is accessible and responsive in the new normal.

Since the BE-LCP is new to the knowledge of everyone in the Department of Education, specifically in the Gamu District, its implementation has been received with questions, with uncertainty, with doubt, and even with fear. Its implementation then posted a challenge most especially to those who are in the ground - the school heads and the

teachers. The very reason why this study is pursued is to know what they could say about the implementation of the BE-LCP, its opportunities, challenges, and effects.

This study is hoped to help the Department of Education as a whole to address pressing issues that she encounters, especially in relation to the delivery of quality education amidst the public health emergency.

Research Questions

This study endeavored to find out the assessment of the elementary and secondary school heads and teachers on the implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) of the Gamu District, the opportunities and challenges in its implementation, and the effect of its implementation to the school performance.

Specifically, this research study sought to answer the following questions:

1. How is the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan implemented in the elementary and secondary schools in Gamu District in terms of:
 - a. Curriculum and Learning Support
 - b. Modular Distance Learning
 - c. Capacity Building
 - d. Requiring Health Standards in School and Workplaces
 - e. Stakeholders' Engagement and Partnership
 - f. Governance and Operations
 - g. Advocacy and Awareness
 - h. Monitoring and Evaluation
2. Is there a significant difference in the implementation of BE-LCP in the elementary and secondary schools?
3. What are the opportunities derived from the implementation of the BE-LCP as perceived by the elementary and secondary schools in terms of:
 - a. Curriculum and Learning Support
 - b. Modular Distance Learning
 - c. Capacity Building
 - d. Requiring Health Standards in School and Workplaces
 - e. Stakeholders' Engagement and Partnership
 - f. Governance and Operations
 - g. Advocacy and Awareness
 - h. Monitoring and Evaluation
4. What are the challenges derived from the implementation of the BE-LCP as perceived by the elementary and secondary schools in terms of:
 - a. Curriculum and Learning Support
 - b. Modular Distance Learning
 - c. Capacity Building
 - d. Requiring Health Standards in School and Workplaces
 - e. Stakeholders' Engagement and Partnership
 - f. Governance and Operations

- g. Advocacy and Awareness
 - h. Monitoring and Evaluation
5. Is there a significant difference in the perception of elementary and secondary schools on the opportunities and challenges derived from the implementation of the BE-LCP?
 6. What is the performance of the schools in terms of the following indicators?
 - a. Enrolment Rate
 - b. Dropout Rate
 - c. Participation Rate
 - d. Completion Rate
 - e. Exit Assessment
 7. How does the implementation of the BE-LCP affect the school performance in terms of the following indicators?
 - a. Enrolment Rate
 - b. Dropout Rate
 - c. Participation Rate
 - d. Completion Rate
 - e. Exit Assessment

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The descriptive research method is employed in this study. Descriptive research according to Voxco (2021) is a powerful research tool that permits the researcher to collect data and describe the demographics of the same with the help of statistical analysis. This method will be used for this study as it attempts to collect information in the implementation of Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) and the opportunities and challenges encountered by the school Heads and teachers both in the elementary and secondary levels at Gamu District.

Locale of the Study

This study is conducted in the public schools in the Municipality of Gamu, Isabela. The municipality is composed of sixteen barangays. The District of Gamu is situated in this municipality. The district has fifteen elementary schools, one primary school, and three secondary schools.

In addition, there is also a Sports Senior High School included in the district. All in all, there are twenty public schools found in the district. The district is under the supervision of a school district supervisor who act as the immediate supervisor of the school heads.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The respondents in this study are the teachers and school heads from the different public schools of the Gamu District. The researcher chose the universal sampling for the respondents.

The table below provides the distribution of teachers and school heads across Gamu District.

Table 1
Frequency Distribution of Respondents

No.	School	No. of Respondents	
		School Head	Teachers
	Secondary		
1.	Gamu Agri-Fishery school	1	67
2.	Gamu Rural School Annex	1	16
3.	Mabini National High School	1	33
4.	Isabela Sports Senior High School	1	7
	Elementary School		
1.	Barcolan Elementary School	1	7
2.	Buenavista Elementary School	1	7
3.	Camp Melchor F. Dela Cruz Elementary School	1	14
4.	Dammao Elementary School	1	7
5.	Furao Elementary School	1	13
6.	Gamu Central School	1	25
7.	Guibang Elementary School	1	11
8.	Lenzon Elementary School	1	7
9.	Linglingay Elementary School	1	7
10.	Mabini Elementary School	1	20
11.	Pintor Elementary School	1	7
12.	Rizal Primary School	1	2
13.	Songsong Elementary School	1	11
14.	Sta. Rosa Elementary School	1	5
15.	Union Elementary School	1	7
16.	Upi Elementary School	1	15
	Total	20	288

Data Gathering Procedure

Following the standard operating procedure for data collection, the researcher assumes responsibility to facilitate the identified protocols. First, the researcher in a letter addressed to the Department of Education, Division of Isabela thru the Schools Division Superintendent requested approval to conduct the study. The same was done with the district supervisor. Second, during the data gathering stage, the researcher personally

floated the questionnaires and collected the data following the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) health protocols and after securing the necessary health documents such as health declaration and travel pass from the rural health unit (RHU). The researcher personally communicated to the identified schools in advance to inform them of their participation in the study and that necessary arrangements were made to accommodate the researcher at the most convenient time and place. Similarly, the respondents were able to prepare themselves. The respondents were given orientation about the purpose of the study. Emphasis that their responses are assured of confidentiality as well as their identity and the school where they belong were greatly considered under the Data Privacy Act.

Statistical Treatment of Data

This study employed the quantitative analysis. The responses retrieved through the questionnaire and documentary analysis will be tallied and computed. Data collected are analyzed and interpreted through the aid of the following statistical tools.

Weighted Mean: This is utilized to determine implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) in the elementary and secondary schools in Gamu District as well as the opportunities and challenges derived from its implementation in terms of curriculum and learning support, modular distance learning, capacity building, requiring health standards in schools and workplaces, stakeholders' engagement and partnership, governance and operations, advocacy and awareness, and monitoring and evaluation.

F-Test: It is used to find out the significant difference in the implementation of BE-LCP and the significant difference in the opportunities and challenges derived from the implementation of the BE-LCP in the elementary and secondary schools.

Rate of Increase and Decrease: These were applied to determine as to how the implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) affected school performance in terms of enrolment rate, dropout rate, participation rate, completion rate, and exit assessment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. The Implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP)

The assessment of the elementary and secondary schools of the Gamu District on the implementation of Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan in different areas are presented in the following tables.

Table 2

The implementation of the Curriculum and Learning Support in elementary and Secondary Schools

Curriculum and Learning Support	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Descriptions	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Descriptions
1. The Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) are unpacked to systematize learning activities and effectively address the varying needs of learners and the challenges of instructional deliveries.	2.94	Fully Implemented	2.85	Fully Implemented
2. The Class Program are made flexible depending on the learning modalities adopted by the school and were consistent with DepEd Order No. 31, s. 2012 or the Policy Guidelines on the Implementation of Grades 1 to 10 of the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum (BEC) Effective School Year 2012-2013 and other existing policies and guidelines on class programming.	2.97	Fully Implemented	2.88	Fully Implemented
3. Weekly Home Learning Plans are prepared by the teachers to ensure that learners are on task and are guided on what they are expected to accomplish within a specific week.	2.97	Fully Implemented	2.98	Fully Implemented
4. The Individual Learning Monitoring Plan is utilized to monitor learners progress, especially to the learners who lag behind as shown by the results of their formative and summative assessments.	2.88	Fully Implemented	2.76	Fully Implemented

5. The school put premium on the instructional management tasks of teachers in their work load or assignment to ensure effective delivery of teaching and learning.	2.91	Fully Implemented	2.85	Fully Implemented
Mean	2.92	Fully Implemented	2.86	Fully Implemented

Table 2 shows the implementation of curriculum and learning support in elementary and secondary schools. Both the elementary and secondary schools assessed that curriculum and learning support are fully implemented having an overall weighted mean of 2.92 and 2.86 respectively. "Weekly Home Learning Plans are prepared by the teachers to ensure that learners are on task and are guided on what they are expected to accomplish within a specific week" has the highest weighted as assessed by the elementary schools with an average of 2.97 and by the secondary schools with an average of 2.98.

Meanwhile, "The Individual Learning Monitoring Plan is utilized to monitor learners progress, especially to the learners who lag behind as shown by the results of their formative and summative assessments" has the lowest weighted mean as assessed by the elementary schools with an average of 2.88 and by the secondary schools with an average of 2.76.

This strengthens the major adjustment made by DepEd to deliver distance learning. One of these adjustments is Streamlining the K to 12 Curriculum into the Most Essential Learning Competencies. By streamlining the learning competencies to the most essential, (the Department) will be able to focus more on the learning activities and resources, while having sufficient time for coverage and mastery. The identification of the MELC is not only in response to the challenge of delivering learning in the time of COVID 19 but is the accelerated result of the curriculum review. It responds to the findings that there are overlaps and congestion in the curriculum.

Table 3

The Implementation of Modular Distance Learning In Elementary and Secondary Schools

Modular Distance Learning	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Descriptions	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Descriptions
1. The school adopts one or a combination of the learning modalities depending on the Covid-19 restrictions and the	2.93	Fully Implemented	2.97	Fully Implemented

particular context of the learners in the school or locality.				
2. The school ensures that all quality learning resources were made available to all learners through reproduction and distribution.	2.98	Fully Implemented	2.83	Fully Implemented
3. Flexibility in finishing the module is accorded to learners with respect to their learning needs, characteristics, and level of understanding to ensure that they have secured mastery of learning contents which is also an essential prerequisite for success in the succeeding modules.	2.92	Fully Implemented	2.89	Fully Implemented
4. Monitoring of learners' progress and setting up of a feedback mechanism is ensured to help learners meet the MELCs while seeing the connection of one lesson to the next to reinforce the coherence of the curriculum.	2.90	Fully Implemented	2.88	Fully Implemented
5. Assessments are implemented consistent with the DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015 or the Policy Guidelines in Classroom Assessment and with DepEd Order No. 31, s. 2020 or the interim Guidelines on Assessment and Grading in Light of the BE-LCP.	2.96	Fully Implemented	2.93	Fully Implemented
Mean	2.93	Fully Implemented	2.90	Fully Implemented

The implementation of modular distance learning in elementary and secondary schools is presented in Table 3. As it is shown, the two school levels assessed the implementation of this area as fully implemented. "The school ensures that all quality learning resources were made available to all learners through reproduction and distribution" has the highest weighted mean as far as the elementary schools are

concerned, with a mean of 2.98. However, this same statement has the lowest weighted mean as assessed by the secondary school, with a mean of 2.83. The statement "The school adopts one or a combination of the learning modalities depending on the Covid-19 restrictions and the particular context of the learners in the school or locality" has the highest weighted mean based on the assessment of the secondary schools, with the average of 2.97. While "Monitoring of learners' progress and setting up of a feedback mechanism is ensured to help learners meet the MELCs while seeing the connection of one lesson to the next to reinforce the coherence of the curriculum" has the lowest weighted mean based on the assessment of the elementary schools, with the average of 2.90.

Tadese and Muluye (2020), in their review to the impact of the covid-19 pandemic on the education system in developing countries found out that the school closure brings difficulties for students, families, and teachers. So, distance learning is a solution to continue the education system.

Toquero (2020), in her study pointed out the effectiveness of distance education. Distance learning highlights the integration of technology for educational delivery. However, what the educational institutions worldwide are applying is an emergency remote education. The former has proven its effectiveness for student learning while the latter is under scrutiny on its concepts. The commonality is that both distance education and emergency remote education make use of technology to provide for learning opportunities. In light of COVID-19, ERE can mitigate educational challenges while in non-traditional classroom settings.

This claim is enhanced by the experience of elementary teachers stating that the use of digital and electronic devices such as computers, mobile phones, and radios were maximized. Added to it is that connection and access to the internet have been prioritized by their schools. These are in order that teachers could still reach out to their learners to follow up and to provide instructions while they are away from each other due to the restrictions cause by the covid-19 pandemic.

Table 4
The Implementation of Capacity Building in Elementary and Secondary Schools

Capacity Building	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Descriptions	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Descriptions
1. Training programs on the management and implementation of Distance Learning Delivery Modalities (DLDMs) were made available to teachers and school heads based on their technology resources map,	2.89	Fully Implemented	2.84	Fully Implemented

readiness assessment results, and implementation plans to prepare them for the 'new normal' in basic education.				
2. The designed capacity building programs are aligned with DM No. 050, s. 2020 which provides professional development priorities for teachers and school leaders for the school year 2020-2023.	2.88	Fully Implemented	2.80	Fully Implemented
3. A support mechanism is established for teachers and school leaders to have access to relevant on-demand technical and administrative advice and guidance.	2.87	Fully Implemented	2.78	Fully Implemented
4. The support mechanism come in the form of coaching, professional learning community through the learning action cell (LAC), resource materials, and other forms of support that can be made available in real or virtual platforms/set-up.	2.91	Fully Implemented	2.87	Fully Implemented
5. Monitoring of course implementation and identification of areas of improvement and best practices is also conducted.	2.90	Fully Implemented	2.86	Fully Implemented
Mean	2.89	Fully Implemented	2.83	Fully Implemented

Table 4 shows the elementary and secondary school teachers assessment on the implementation of capacity building. They assessed that this area is fully implemented based on the general weighted mean of 2.89 in the elementary schools and 2.83 in the secondary schools.

"The support mechanism come in the form of coaching, professional learning community through the learning action cell (LAC), resource materials, and other forms of

support that can be made available in real or virtual platforms/ set-up" got the highest mean of 2.91 in elementary and 2.87 in secondary. Meanwhile, the statement " A support mechanism is established for teachers and school leaders to have access to relevant on-demand technical and administrative advice and guidance" got the lowest mean in both basic education levels, that is 2.87 in elementary and 2.78 in secondary. However, both weighted mean is interpreted as fully implemented.

It goes to show DepEd's commitment that "teachers and school leaders shall be capacitated to implement and manage the adoption of multi-modal learning delivery models based on their technology resources map, readiness assessment results, and implementation plans. They will be introduced to a range of delivery modalities they can utilize depending on the context of their community and the situation of learners and teachers. Tools and mechanisms will also be provided for them to make informed decisions on appropriate learning delivery mode for their context. Context includes geographical conditions, access to delivery platforms (i.e. online, broadcast technology, and modules), readiness of learners, teachers and household and community partners, and other relevant factors." In addition, the re-skilling of teachers on the different modalities and strategies while facing the new normal in education, according to the teachers, was a key to the success of the BE-LCP implementation. The implementation of the learning delivery modalities under the BE-LCP entails the provision of corresponding training to teachers and school leaders.

Table 5

The Implementation of Requiring Health Standards in School and Workplaces in Elementary and Secondary Schools

Requiring Health Standards in School and Workplaces	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Descriptions	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Descriptions
1. The Health and Safety Guidelines in the School and the Workplace is in accordance with the DOH Guidelines on the Risk-Based Public Health Standards for Covid-19 Mitigation (DOH AO No. 2020-0015) and the Guidelines on the Required Health Standards in Basic Education Offices and Schools (DO No. 14, s. 2020).	2.90	Fully Implemented	2.94	Fully Implemented
2. The school implements strategies to increase physical and mental	2.86	Fully Implemented	2.80	Fully Implemented

resilience of all learners and personnel.				
3. The school implements strategies to reduce transmission of Covid-19.	2.93	Fully Implemented	2.94	Fully Implemented
4. The school implements strategies to reduce contact.	2.92	Fully Implemented	2.93	Fully Implemented
5. The school implements strategies to reduce duration of infection.	2.92	Fully Implemented	2.92	Fully Implemented
Mean	2.91	Fully Implemented	2.91	Fully Implemented

Table 5 presents the respondents' assessment on the implementation of requiring health standards in school and workplaces in elementary and secondary. The table further shows that this area in the implementation of BE-LCP is fully implemented as evidenced by the general weighted mean of 2.91 both in elementary and secondary schools.

The statement "The school implements strategies to reduce transmission of Covid-19" has the highest mean among the given statements as assessed by both the elementary and secondary teachers, with the average of 2.93 and 2.94 respectively. The statement "The school implements strategies to increase physical and mental resilience of all learners and personnel" has the lowest mean of 2.86 and 2.80 in the elementary and secondary. These, however, are still interpreted as fully implemented.

This is affirmed by the elementary and secondary teachers claiming that they tried to implement the basic health standards to prevent the further spread of the corona virus, most especially by observing the one to two meters social distancing while in the workplace or common area.

Table 6

The Implementation of Stakeholders' Engagement and Partnership in Elementary and Secondary Schools

Stakeholders' Engagement and Partnership	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Descriptions	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Descriptions
1. The school's localized <i>Brigada Eskwela</i> Program highlighted partnership with stakeholders that complement the Department's efforts for	2.88	Fully Implemented	2.95	Fully Implemented

ensuring that quality education continues, despite the challenges in adapting to the 'new normal'.				
2. Orientation activities with teachers, partners, PTA, and learners on BE-LCP focused on the implementation of DepEd's multiple learning modalities.	2.88	Fully Implemented	2.87	Fully Implemented
3. Parents and the community are encouraged through the Parent-Teachers Association (PTA), barangay officials, and other stakeholders towards possible collaborations with the school that can support the delivery of learning while adapting to the 'new normal'.	2.90	Fully Implemented	2.88	Fully Implemented
4. The school updates emergency and contingency plans, and communicates to all stakeholders how they can support schools to ensure resiliency in relation to school safety and preparedness as provided for under DepEd Memo No. 32, s. 2020 or the 2020 <i>Brigada Eskwela</i> Program Implementing Guidelines.	2.87	Fully Implemented	2.92	Fully Implemented
5. The school engages partners extensively and substantially in <i>Brigada Eskwela</i> to promote quality education and commit their support for the 'new normal' especially in the delivery of learning.	2.89	Fully Implemented	2.96	Fully Implemented
Mean	2.88	Fully Implemented	2.92	Fully Implemented

Table 6 shows the implementation of stakeholders' engagement and partnership in elementary and secondary schools. The table also shows that, based on the general

weighted mean of 2.88 in elementary schools and 2.92 in secondary schools, this area in the implementation of the BE-LCP is fully implemented.

With a weighted mean of 2.90, elementary schools gave the statement "Parents and the community are encouraged through the Parent-Teachers Association (PTA), barangay officials, and other stakeholders towards possible collaborations with the school that can support the delivery of learning while adapting to the 'new normal'" with the highest regard, while the statement "The school engages partners extensively and substantially in Brigada Eskwela to promote quality education and commit their support for the 'new normal' especially in the delivery of learning", with an average of 2.96 assessed the highest by the secondary schools.

The statement "The school updates emergency and contingency plan and communicates to all stakeholders how they can support schools to ensure resiliency in relation to school safety and preparedness as provided for und DepEd Memo No. 32, s. 2020 or the 2020 Brigada Eskwela Program Implementing Guidelines" has the lowest mean in elementary schools, a the statement "Orientation activities with teachers, partners, PTA, learners on BE-LCP focused on the implementation of DepEd's multiple learning modalities" in secondary school. Both has the weighted mean of 2 but still interpreted as fully implemented.

As it was seen by the secondary teachers, this affirms what Malaluan (2020) reported that the Philippine government, through its Congress, is strongly supporting the DepEd's LCP implementation. Aside from government support, the department has also received support from various partners as evident in its forged partnerships with numerous individuals and organizations.

The success in the implementation of the BE-LCP, according to the secondary school teachers, was due to the good rapport between the school and the stakeholders - the parents, local government officials, and members of the alumni. Thus the opportune event made the partnership with stakeholders became more intense and visible.

Table 7

The Implementation of Governance and Operations in Elementary and Secondary Schools

Governance and Operations	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Descriptions	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Descriptions
1. The school is provided with technical assistance in the implementation of the BE-LCP.	2.87	Fully Implemented	2.85	Fully Implemented
2. The school secured personnel financial stability through timely process of	2.88	Fully Implemented	2.96	Fully Implemented

salary, allowances, and benefits.				
3. The school ensures its capacity to continuously improve and be strategic in managing the environment for which teaching and learning takes place in the new normal'.	2.93	Fully Implemented	2.95	Fully Implemented
4. The school makes necessary adjustments to maximize the available funds for the implementation of programs, projects, and activities captures in the BE-LCP that require more funding support.	2.88	Fully Implemented	2.89	Fully Implemented
5. The school implements appropriate work arrangements to facilitate the safe return of teaching and nonteaching personnel in accordance with DepEd Order No. 11, s. 2020.	2.90	Fully Implemented	2.95	Fully Implemented
Mean	2.89	Fully Implemented	2.92	Fully Implemented

Table 7 illustrates the implementation of governance and operations in elementary and secondary schools. As it is seen both elementary and secondary schools assessed this area as fully implemented, with a general weighted mean of 2.89 in elementary and 2.92 in secondary.

Based on the assessment by the elementary and secondary schools, the statement “The school is provided with technical assistance in the implementation of the BE-LCP” got the lowest weighted mean of 2.87 and 2.85 respectively. However, it may have received the lowest, it is still interpreted as fully implemented.

As expressed both by the elementary and secondary teachers, though there was help, technical assistance came in already during the implementation of the BE-LCP. It should have come, according to them, before its implementation, so that they have, at least, made the necessary preparations.

The statement that got the highest weighted mean in the elementary schools is “The school ensures its capacity to continuously improve and be strategic in managing the environment for which teaching and learning takes place in the new normal”, while “The school secured personnel financial stability through timely process of salary,

allowances, and benefits” in the secondary schools. The weighted mean in the elementary schools is 2.93 and 2.96 in secondary schools.

Table 8

The Implementation of Advocacy and Awareness in Elementary and Secondary Schools

Advocacy and Awareness	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Descriptions	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Descriptions
1. The communication efforts of the school for the BE-LCP are anchored on the core principles of proactive, cooperative responsive and highly engaged relationship with its stakeholders and the public.	2.86	Fully Implemented	2.89	Fully Implemented
2. The school conducts information dissemination to persons concerned such as parents, barangay officials, and the rest of the community on the flexible learning options and the strategies in implementing distance learning.	2.87	Fully Implemented	2.95	Fully Implemented
3. The school explained the new role and increased involvement of parents and other stakeholders in the delivery and in the learning of their children.	2.90	Fully Implemented	2.91	Fully Implemented
4. The school utilizes and maximizes possible means of communication such as online platforms and local radio stations in the dissemination of truthful and accurate information and to address queries relative to BE-LCP.	2.86	Fully Implemented	2.94	Fully Implemented
5. The school established a Help Desk to address issues and concerns relative to BE-LCP.	2.78	Fully Implemented	2.82	Fully Implemented

Mean	2.85	Fully Implemented	2.90	Fully Implemented
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Table 8 exemplifies the implementation of advocacy and awareness in elementary and secondary schools. The table displays that the two group of respondents assessed this area of the BE-LCP as fully implemented based on the general weighted mean of 2.85 by the elementary teachers and 2.90 by the secondary teachers.

The highest weighted mean in the elementary schools is 2.90, which is interpreted as fully implemented, exemplified in the statement “The school explained the new role and increased involvement of parents and other stakeholders in the delivery and in the learning of their children.” In the secondary schools, the highest weighted mean is 2.95, which is also interpreted as fully implemented, in the statement “The school conducts information dissemination to persons concerned such as parents, barangay officials, and the rest of the community on the flexible learning options and the strategies in implementing distance learning.”

This shows that, according to the respondents, they felt the need to reach out to schools’ external stakeholders and inform them of the peculiarity of the educational situation and their roles in the educative process of the children. According to the elementary teachers, since the learning modality is distance learning through the use of modules, parents need to be informed that, in the new normal, they will become really the co-advisers as well as the co-subject teachers of their children, as they will provide instructions in accomplishing and answering the various tasks and activities provided in the self-learning modules. Furthermore, as secondary teachers stated, they did information dissemination through visiting parents and other stakeholders and gathering them in barangay halls or gymnasiums while observing health protocols to discuss about the continuity and new ways of learning during the pandemic.

Table 9
The Implementation of Monitoring and Evaluation in Elementary and Secondary Schools

Advocacy and Awareness	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Descriptions	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Descriptions
1. A Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) team is organized to monitor and supervise the operationalization of the BE-LCP in the school.	2.86	Fully Implemented	2.82	Fully Implemented
2. The M&E focused on curriculum implementation and management in light of Covid-19 pandemic and on	2.87	Fully Implemented	2.90	Fully Implemented

school operations and management of resources.				
3. The school head is primarily responsible in the M&E of the implementation of programmed projects and activities in the BE-LCP, ensuring that all targets are achieved and delivered in the school.	2.89	Fully Implemented	2.92	Fully Implemented
4. Teachers assisted in looking into the implementation of the programmed activities and projects and other school activities aligned with the BE-LCP.	2.88	Fully Implemented	2.91	Fully Implemented
5. Results of the M&E is communicated to the Public School District Supervisor's Office and other persons concerned for the improvement of the design and systems of the BE-LCP.	2.87	Fully Implemented	2.88	Fully Implemented
Mean	2.87	Fully Implemented	2.89	Fully Implemented

Table 9 illustrates the implementation of monitoring and evaluation in the elementary and secondary schools of the BE-LCP. As it is shown in the table, the general weighted mean, as assessed by elementary schools is 2.87 and 2.89 by secondary schools. Both assessments are interpreted as fully implemented.

The statement "The school head is primarily responsible in the M&E of the implementation of programmed projects and activities in the BE-LCP, ensuring that all targets are achieved and delivered in the school" got the highest weighted mean from both groups of respondents; 2.89 in elementary schools and 2.92 in secondary school. Additionally, the statement that has the lowest weighted mean in the elementary and secondary schools is "A Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) team is organized to monitor and supervise the operationalization of the BE-LCP in the school." 2.86 is the weighted mean in elementary schools and 2.82 in the secondary schools.

Elementary and secondary schools believed that the school heads have the upper hand in making sure that the BE-LCP are paved to reach its purpose. However, as they have observed, the school heads could not do the task alone. This is why, according to them, they also see the need that the head has to have arms, a monitoring and evaluation team, to assist them in looking into the enactment of programmed activities and projects aligned in the implementation of the BE-LCP, as well as in communicating to other

stakeholders and superiors concerned about the results of the monitoring and evaluation. Some schools, though, failed to create a functioning monitoring and evaluation team.

2. The Perception of the Elementary and Secondary Schools on the Implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP)

The perception of the elementary schools and secondary schools of the Gamu District on the implementation of Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan in the different areas is presented in the following table.

Table 10
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of Elementary and Secondary School Teachers in the Implementation of the BE-LCP

Implementation of the BE-LCP on the following Areas	Mean		Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
	Elementary School Teachers	Secondary School Teachers			
Curriculum and Learning Support	2.92	2.86	0.0008	Reject Ho	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	2.93	2.90	0.0001	Reject Ho	Significant
Capacity Building	2.89	2.83	0.0022	Reject Ho	Significant
Requiring Health Standards in Schools and Workplaces	2.91	2.91	0.1904	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Stakeholders' Engagement and Partnership	2.88	2.92	0.0040	Reject Ho	Significant
Governance and Operation	2.89	2.92	0.0099	Reject Ho	Significant
Advocacy and Awareness	2.85	2.90	0.0007	Reject Ho	Significant
Monitoring and Evaluation	2.87	2.89	0.0146	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 10 discloses the results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the elementary and secondary school teachers in the implementation of the BE-LCP.

The results show that the probability values of F are less than 0.05 except for the requiring health standards in school and work places. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is significant difference in the perception of the elementary and secondary school teachers in the implementation of the BE-LCP

along curriculum and learning support, modular distance learning, capacity building, stakeholders' engagement and partnership, governance and operation, advocacy and awareness, and monitoring and evaluation. It implies that the two groups of teachers perceive differently the implementation of the BE-LCP along these areas. It states further that they vary in their responses in implementing the said areas of the BE-LCP. The researcher further infers that the elementary school teachers have better perception on the implementation of the BE-LCP along curriculum and learning support, modular distance learning, and capacity building for they have higher mean responses. While, the secondary school teachers have better perception on the implementation of BE-LCP along stakeholders' engagement and partnership, governance and operation, advocacy and awareness, and monitoring and evaluation since they obtained higher means.

However, there is no significant difference in the perception of the elementary and secondary school teachers on the implementation of the BE-LCP along the requiring health standards in schools and workplaces. It shows that the two groups of teachers do not vary in their perception on the implementation of the BE-LCP along this area. It is inferred further that the elementary and secondary school teachers have similar responses in implementing the BE-LCP along the said area.

3. Opportunities Derived from the Implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP)

The perception of the elementary and secondary school of the Gamu District on the opportunities derived from the implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan in the different areas are presented in the following tables.

Table 11
Perception on the Opportunities in the Implementation of Curriculum and Learning Support by the Elementary And Secondary Schools

Curriculum and Learning Support Statements	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. The unpacking and combining of Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) helps to systematize learning activities and effectively address the varying needs of learners and the challenges of instructional deliveries.	3.85	Very Much	3.80	Very Much
2. Unpacking of content and performance standard results in a form of more easily translated into unit and daily lesson plans help	3.79	Very Much	3.73	Very Much

educators zero-in on what is essential for instruction.				
3. The streamlined competencies include the 21 st century skills, interpersonal skills, leadership skills, and global cross-cultural awareness.	3.77	Very Much	3.78	Very Much
4. Holistic intervention is ensured through the implementation of the following components : Teachers Learning Resources, Learning Environment, Assessment and Exits, School Leadership and Management, Community/Industry Relevance and Partnership.	3.76	Very Much	3.70	Very Much
Mean	3.79	Very Much	3.75	Very Much

Table 11 presents the perception of elementary and secondary schools on the opportunities in the implementation of curriculum and learning support. As the table shows, this area in the implementation of the BE-LCP is very much an opportunity with a general weighted mean of 3.79 by the elementary and 3.75 by the secondary schools.

The statement with the highest weighted mean as assessed by the elementary and secondary schools is “The unpacking and combining of Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) helps to systematize learning activities and effectively address the varying needs of learners and the challenges of instructional deliveries.” The weighted of this statement in the elementary schools is 3.85 while 3.80 in the secondary schools.

According to elementary teachers, unpacking the most essential learning competencies is very essential as it can help in the execution of the lessons from basic to complex. As to the secondary teachers, they also seen the importance of unpacking the competencies, as, they claimed, that it is essential in order to have a meaningful and systematic learning activity so that the competencies needed by the learners are not congested.

Meanwhile, the statement with the lowest weighted mean is the “Holistic intervention is ensured through the implementation of the following components: Teachers Learning Resources, Learning Environment, Assessment and Exits, School Leadership and Management, Community/Industry Relevance and Partnership.” The weighted of this statement in the elementary schools is 3.76 while 3.70 in the secondary schools. This statement may have garnered the lowest weighted mean, yet it is still considered as very much an opportunity by the two groups of respondents.

Table 12

Perception on the Opportunities in the Implementation of Modular Distance Learning by the Elementary And Secondary Schools

Modular Distance Learning Statements	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. The individualized instruction allows learners to use self-learning modules (SLMs) in print or digital format/electronic copy, whichever is applicable in the context of the learner, and other learning resources like learner's materials, textbooks, activity sheets, study guides and other study materials.	3.85	Very Much	3.85	Very Much
2. Learners can access electronic copies of learning materials on a computer, tablet, personal computer, or smartphone; CDs, DVDs, flash drive storage and computer-based applications are also used to deliver e-learning materials, including offline e-books.	3.53	Very Much	3.58	Very Much
3. The subject teacher is able to monitor the progress of the learners through varied innovative assessment strategies responsive to the current health crisis.	3.72	Very Much	3.78	Very Much
4. The learners are provided with assistance from the subject teachers via e-mail, telephone, text messages, Facebook messenger, etc.	3.79	Very Much	3.81	Very Much
Mean	3.72	Very Much	3.76	Very Much

Table 12 shows the perception on the opportunities in the implementation of modular distance learning by the elementary and secondary schools. The table, further, shows that the elementary and secondary schools perceive this area in the implementation of the BE-LCP as very much an opportunity as evidenced by the general weighted mean of 3.72 by the elementary schools and 3.76 by the secondary schools.

With regards to the statement that has the highest weighted mean, elementary and secondary schools had equal perception on "The individualized instruction allows learners

to use self-learning modules (SLMs) in print or digital format/electronic copy, whichever is applicable in the context of the learner, and other learning resources like learner’s materials, textbooks, activity sheets, study guides and other study materials.” The weighted mean of this statement is 3.85, both in the elementary and secondary schools.

The provision of self-learning modules to the learners is very essential to the continuity of learning during the time of the covid-19 pandemic, according to the elementary teachers. Learners will be able to continue with their studies at the safety of their homes with the help of their parents or guardians, they said. Furthermore, the use of these modules, according to secondary school teachers, will ensure accessibility of learners to quality basic education amidst the prohibition of face-to-face classes due to the health situation.

The statement with the lowest weighted mean both in elementary and secondary schools is “Learners can access electronic copies of learning materials on a computer, tablet, personal computer, or smartphone; CDs, DVDs, flash drive storage and computer-based applications are also used to deliver e-learning materials, including offline e-books.” The weighted mean in elementary schools is 3.53 and in secondary schools is 3.58. However, this is still assessed as very much an opportunity.

Table 13
Perception on the Opportunities in the Implementation of Capacity Building by the Elementary And Secondary Schools

Capacity Building Statements	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. The needs of the DepEd personnel and stakeholders are addressed through a comprehensive capability building program that was crafted.	3.71	Very Much	3.69	Very Much
2. School officials are updated through series of Webinars.	3.77	Very Much	3.76	Very Much
3. Trainers are trained to create pool of experts who can serve as resource persons in the conduct of varied capability building programs.	3.76	Very Much	3.73	Very Much
4. Key officials and personnel are capacitated through online trainings.	3.76	Very Much	3.80	Very Much
Mean	3.75	Very Much	3.74	Very Much

Table 13 illustrates the perception of the elementary and secondary schools on the opportunities in the implementation of capacity building. It further shows that this part of BE-LCP is very much an opportunity as seen in the table the general weighted mean of 3.75 in the elementary schools and 3.74 in the secondary schools.

In the part of elementary schools, the statement that has the highest weighted mean, which is 3.77, is that “School officials are updated through series of Webinars.” In the secondary schools, it is the statement “Key officials and personnel are capacitated through online trainings” with a weighted mean of 3.80. Both statements are considered as very much opportunities.

The results affirm the study of Leech, et al. (2020) that across grade levels and content areas, teachers need additional trainings and resources pertaining to teaching and assessing learning in a remote setting. Providing professional development to all teachers, but to elementary teachers in particular, could help to mitigate the challenges these teachers report experiencing in delivering remote instruction to their students. Technology trainings would provide the opportunity for teachers to feel more confident in their remote instruction, to provide higher quality and more effective remote instruction to their students, and to increase student learning and development.

It is also an affirmation to the study of Jamon, et al. (2021) that according to the teachers they need training on the new normal pedagogies. The public school teachers admitted that they are strangers in terms of the current situation of the Philippine educational system. They are “pedagogical and content knowledge experts” in face-to-face classes, but covid-19 outbreak in the Philippines compelled all the educational institutions to change the mode of learning from face to face to online, modular, and blended learning.

Table 14

Perception on the Opportunities in the Implementation of Requiring Health Standards to Increase Physical and Mental Resilience By the Elementary and Secondary Schools

Requiring Health Standards to Increase Physical and Mental Resilience Statements	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. There is regular and safe delivery of essential school services, continuous promotion of “school-life balance”, and learners’ engagement in daily physical activities through the observance of the required Health Standards.	3.80	Very Much	3.82	Very Much
2. Priority on the protection and promotion of mental health and	3.81	Very Much	3.73	Very Much

general welfare of all learners and personnel are upheld.				
3. There are interventions to increase mental health within the first week of return to school, operationalization of a guidance office to provide basic mental health services to learners and personnel, and the establishment of counseling services through hotline or online platforms.	3.73	Very Much	3.68	Very Much
Mean	3.78	Very Much	3.75	Very Much

Table 14 displays the perception of the respondents on the opportunities in the implementation of requiring health standards to increase physical and mental resilience. As the table shows, this area in the implementation of the BE-LCP is very much an opportunity based on the results of the general weighted mean in the elementary and secondary schools. It has a general weighted mean of 3.78 in the elementary schools and 3.75 in the secondary schools.

The statement that has the highest weighted mean in the elementary is “Priority on the protection and promotion of mental health and general welfare of all learners and personnel are upheld,” while “There is regular and safe delivery of essential school services, continuous promotion of ‘school-life balance’, and learners’ engagement in daily physical activities through the observance of the required health standards” in secondary schools.

According to the elementary teachers, during the new normal, aside from attending to the academic needs of the learners, great attention was also provided to the protection and promotion of their mental health and that of the employees as they claimed that mental health is an integral component of health and well-being, and that it influences academic and work performance. Speaking of academic and work performance, another factors that could influence these in the school setting are the promotion of ‘school-life balance’ and engagement in physical activities. This has been underscored by the secondary schools as they believe that not maintaining such a state of balance makes studying, efficiency in task completion, and moving through the day becomes much more difficult.

Table 15

Perception on the Opportunities in the Implementation of Requiring Health Standards to Reduce Transmission by the Elementary and Secondary Schools

Requiring Health Standards to Reduce Transmission Statements	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. There is reduced transmission in the school through the implementation of appropriate information and education campaigns on proper handwashing, and respiratory etiquette are implemented.	3.90	Very Much	3.86	Very Much
2. Handwashing stations or lavatories were set up and disinfectants were provided for personal disinfection.	3.87	Very Much	3.88	Very Much
3. Institutionalized routine cleaning and disinfecting of workstations and touch areas such as toilets, doorknobs, switches at least once every day for workstations are observed.	3.77	Very Much	3.79	Very Much
Mean	3.85	Very Much	3.84	Very Much

Table 15 shows the perception on the opportunities in the implementation of requiring health standards to reduce transmission by the elementary and secondary schools. This portion in the implementation of the BE-LCP is assessed as very much an opportunity as presented in the table with the general weighted mean of 3.85 and 3.84 in the elementary and secondary respectively.

As the table shows, the statement that has the highest weighted mean is the “There is reduced transmission in the school through the implementation of appropriate information and education campaigns on proper handwashing, and respiratory etiquette are implemented” in the elementary, with a weighted mean of 3.90, while in the secondary schools is “Handwashing stations or lavatories were set up and disinfectants were provided for personal disinfection” with a weighted mean of 3.88. both statements are described as very much to be opportunities in the implementation of BE-LCP.

The elementary teachers claimed that they were able to safeguard themselves from the deadly virus and reduce its transmission while in their respective workplaces due to constant reminding of their colleagues and visitors of the minimum health standards to

be observed like proper handwashing before entering the school premises, frequent sanitation of their hands and work stations, and wearing of face masks at all times. On the side of the secondary schools, they complied to the mandate and put up washing stations near the gates of the school. Here, they said, personnel and visitors alike will wash their hands before going in and leaving the school so as to be sanitized and possible transmission of the virus will be avoided in and outside the school. In addition, they claimed that putting up such facilities made a big help in keeping their campuses free from the corona virus.

The strict observance of personal hygiene, which are handwashing with soap and water, and sanitizing with hand disinfectants, as well as environmental hygiene, that is disinfecting surfaces and objects, are, according to the teachers, a much-needed practice to continue so that the spread of the covid-19 will be contained and that schools could get back to normal again.

Meanwhile, the statement that has the lowest weighted mean, both in the elementary and secondary schools is “Institutionalized routine cleaning and disinfecting of workstations and touch areas such as toilets, doorknobs, switches at least once every day for workstations are observed,” with a mean of 3.77 in the elementary schools and 3.79 in secondary schools.

Table 16

Perception on the Opportunities in the Implementation of Requiring Health Standards to Reduce Contact by the Elementary and Secondary Schools

Requiring Health Standards to Reduce Contact Statements	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Travel and activities of learners and personnel is limited to those most essentials.	3.84	Very Much	3.87	Very Much
2. Online platforms for meetings, trainings, conferences are utilized instead of face-to-face.	3.87	Very Much	3.89	Very Much
3. Revised policy on alternative work arrangements (AWA) to minimize contact in the school through DepEd Order No.11, s. 2020 (Revised Guidelines on Alternative Work Arrangements in the Department of Education During the Period of State of National emergency Due to COVID-19 Pandemic) is enforced.	3.74	Very Much	3.79	Very Much
Mean	3.81	Very Much	3.85	Very Much

Table 16 illustrates the perception of the elementary and secondary schools on the opportunities in the implementation of requiring health standards to reduce contact. The respondents assessed this part in the implementation of the BE-LCP as very much an opportunity. In elementary schools, it has a general weighted mean of 3.81 and 3.85 in secondary schools.

Of the three statements, “Online platforms for meetings, trainings, conferences are utilized instead of face-to-face” got the highest weighted mean, both in the elementary and secondary schools. In the elementary, it has a weighted mean of 3.87, while in the secondary it is 3.89; both are interpreted as very much an opportunity.

The utilization of online platforms, according to the elementary and secondary teachers, was a welcome development in the continuity of learning amidst the pandemic. This, they said, is a practical solution for class instructions to learners and capacity building for teachers where face-to-face meetings and gatherings are nearly impossible due to social distancing policies. Furthermore, they claimed that this strategy served its purpose of limiting the physical contact of learners to their teachers and vice versa, and school employees to other stakeholders because of community quarantines in order to contain the spread of the virus.

Table 17
Perception on the Opportunities in the Implementation of Requiring Health Standards to Reduce Duration of Infection by the Elementary and Secondary Schools

Requiring Health Standards to Reduce Duration of Infection Statements	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. To reduce the duration of infection of COVID-19, early detection and isolation of symptomatic individuals are ensured in the school.	3.83	Very Much	3.86	Very Much
2. The school ensures the establishment/setting-up/refurbishment of its own clinic for health assessment for the provision of appropriate interventions such as first aid or treatment, and proper management of symptoms of learners, teachers, personnel, and, when capable, of visitors.	3.69	Very Much	3.82	Very Much
Mean	3.76	Very Much	3.84	Very Much

Table 17 presents the perception on the opportunities in the implementation of requiring health standards to reduce duration of infection by the elementary and secondary schools. As part in the implementation of the BE-LCP, this area is perceived to be very much an opportunity by the respondents. In the elementary, general weighted mean is 3.76, and in the secondary schools is 3.84.

“To reduce the duration of infection of COVID-19, early detection and isolation of symptomatic individuals are ensured in the school” has the highest weighted mean, both in the elementary and secondary schools, of the two statements in this area of the BE-LCP. It has a weighted mean of 3.83 in elementary and 3.86 in the secondary.

This, according to the respondents, was the primary purpose of putting up triage area near or at the gates of the schools. Secondary teachers claimed that when trained personnel in their schools detects employees or visitors that have symptoms of infection, they do not let them enter the school, instead they place them in an isolation room for observation and for referral to a medical facility nearby, so as not to infect other school employees should they carry the virus for precautionary measures.

The results presented in Tables 14, 15, 16, and 17 realize the goal set by DepEd Order No. 14, s. 2020 that sets the guidelines on the required standards in basic education offices and schools. This Order was issued by DepEd for the guidance of all learners, teachers, and non-teaching personnel nationwide to ensure the safe return to schools and DepEd offices when allowed by the Department of Health (DOH), the Inter-Agency Task Force for the Management of Emerging Infectious Diseases (IATF), or the Office of the President.

Table 18

Perception on the Opportunities in the Implementation of Stakeholders’ Engagement and Partnership by the Elementary and Secondary Schools

Stakeholders’ Engagement and Partnership Statements	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Convergence of all education sectors was strengthened in support to the implementation of the BE-LCP.	3.80	Very Much	3.80	Very Much
2. Alignment of Special Education Fund (SEF) to support the Learning Continuity Plan (LCP) of the school was encouraged.	3.79	Very Much	3.71	Very Much
3. Prioritization of SEF to support the learning modalities but not limited to learning materials and equipment for	3.80	Very Much	3.75	Very Much

students and teachers was enforced.				
4. All Local Government Units (LGUs), National Government Agencies (NGAs), Non-Government Organizations (NGOs), and Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) partnership for the implementation of the DepEd Minimum Health Standards were collaboratively set-up.	3.76	Very Much	3.80	Very Much
5. The national schools' maintenance week (<i>Brigada Eskwela</i>) has been conducted which includes cleaning, minor repairs, repainting, beautification, landscaping, electrical works and installations, pruning of trees, and other activities.	3.83	Very Much	3.87	Very Much
6. <i>Oplan Balik Eskwela</i> was strengthened to ensure that learners are properly informed of the learning opportunities amidst COVID-19 to address enrollment-related problems, queries, and other concerns commonly encountered by the public.	3.77	Very Much	3.85	Very Much
7. <i>Oplan Kalusugan</i> has been strengthened to ensure health conditions of learners during this time of pandemic through stakeholders' support.	3.77	Very Much	3.74	Very Much
Mean	3.79	Very Much	3.79	Very Much

Table 18 shows perception of the elementary and secondary schools on the opportunities in the implementation of stakeholders' engagement and partnership. As further shown in the table, the elementary and secondary schools have an identical general weighted mean of 3.79 and is described as very much an opportunity in the implementation of the BE-LCP.

The statement that has the highest weighted mean among the rest is "The national schools' maintenance week (*Brigada Eskwela*) has been conducted which includes cleaning, minor repairs, repainting, beautification, landscaping, electrical works and installations, pruning of trees, and other activities," both in the elementary and secondary

schools. The weighted mean in elementary is 3.83 while in the secondary schools is 3.87, and they are assessed as very much an opportunity.

Secondary school teachers observed that the *Brigada Eskwela* mobilized both the internal and external stakeholders of the schools as they render their time and skills to do classroom repairs, maintenance work, and clean-up of public elementary and secondary schools; making the schools ready before the opening of classes even in the midst of the pandemic. Everything was done, of course, while observing the minimum health standards, they added. In addition, elementary school teachers underscore its importance by claiming that *Brigada Eskwela* saves resources on the part of the school as most resources being used are generated through donations.

Table 19

Perception on the Opportunities in the Implementation of Governance and Operations by the Elementary and Secondary Schools

Governance and Operations Statements	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Technical assistance to the school were provided; and Quality Assurance & Monitoring Evaluation (QAME) is established to quality assure, monitor and evaluate programs, projects and activities.	3.81	Very Much	3.84	Very Much
2. Personnel welfare and benefit have been given priority in terms of on-time release of salary, allowances and other benefits.	3.79	Very Much	3.81	Very Much
3. There is effective and efficient procurement process that has been observed in the reproduction of SLMs.	3.78	Very Much	3.77	Very Much
Mean	3.79	Very Much	3.81	Very Much

Table 19 illustrates the perception on the opportunities in the implementation of governance and operations by the elementary and secondary schools. Based on the table, all the statements were perceived to be very much opportunities in the implementation of the BE-LCP. Furthermore, it can be noticed that the elementary and secondary schools both assessed this very much an opportunity with overall weighted means of 3.79 and 3.81 respectively.

The statement that has the highest weighted mean in both elementary and secondary is “Technical assistance to the school were provided; and Quality Assurance

& Monitoring Evaluation (QAME) is established to quality assure, monitor and evaluate programs, projects and activities.” In the elementary, its weighted mean is 3.81 and in the secondary, it is 3.84.

Elementary teachers claimed that technical assistance were provided by the personnel coming from the district and division offices. They offer assistance to school leaders and teachers in order for them to become effective in their function as education providers in the new normal. In the same manner, secondary school teachers recognized the importance of technical assistance as deemed necessary to ensure effective program implementation to achieve better learning outcomes.

Table 20

Perception on the Opportunities in the Implementation of Advocacy and Awareness by the Elementary and Secondary Schools

Advocacy and Awareness Statements	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Social media platforms like Facebook have been maximized to disseminate relevant information regarding issues and concerns affecting learning.	3.79	Very Much	3.85	Very Much
2. Establishment of webpage or group chats (Facebook Messenger) have helped in disseminating memoranda, advisories, and other information related to the implementation of BE-LCP and Distance Learning Modalities.	3.81	Very Much	3.87	Very Much
Mean	3.80	Very Much	3.86	Very Much

Table 20 demonstrates the opportunities in the implementation of advocacy and awareness as perceived by elementary and secondary schools. As the table presents, this area is perceived by the two sets of respondents as very much an opportunity in the implementation of the BE-LCP as evidenced by the general weighted mean of 3.80 in the elementary and 3.86 in the secondary.

“Establishment of webpage or group chats (Facebook Messenger) have helped in disseminating memoranda, advisories, and other information related to the implementation of BE-LCP and Distance Learning Modalities” is the statement that has the highest weighted mean from among the two statements in this area, both in elementary and secondary schools. The weighted mean in elementary is 3.81, while in the secondary is 3.87.

Both elementary and secondary school teachers emphasized the importance of communication this time of the pandemic, where face-to-face conversation is not permitted, through the use of technologies and online platforms. They said that communication plays a major role in getting the support of stakeholders in implementing the BE-LCP. This is the reason why schools, as the teachers claimed, made use of the available, economic, practical, and familiar-to-everyone online platforms in the dissemination of important announcements by DepEd or by the schools and other information in relation to the implementation of the BE-LCP.

Additionally, one factor that led to the successful implementation of the BE-LCP per the secondary school teachers is the well-established communication between the teachers, learners, and parents or guardians using various digital and online platforms such as the text messages, electronic mails, and social media in disseminating relevant information, memoranda, advisories and others.

Table 21

Perception on the Opportunities in the Implementation of Monitoring and Evaluation by the Elementary and Secondary Schools

Monitoring and Evaluation Statements	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of the school's BE-LCP is ensured through the establishment of the Monitoring and Evaluation team.	3.82	Very Much	3.80	Very Much
2. Follow-up ensures effective resolutions to all issues and concerns.	3.80	Very Much	3.78	Very Much
Mean	3.81	Very Much	3.79	Very Much

Table 21 exemplifies the elementary and secondary schools' perception on the opportunities in the implementation of monitoring and evaluation. As it is seen in the table, the general weighted mean in elementary schools is 3.81 and 3.79 in the secondary schools; both are described as very much an opportunity in the implementation of the BE-LCP.

With 3.82 weighted mean in the elementary schools and 3.80 in the secondary schools, of the two statements, "Monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of the school's BE-LCP is ensured through the establishment of the Monitoring and Evaluation team" is the statement that has the highest weighted mean in this part.

According to the teachers, elementary and secondary alike, claimed that Quality Assurance & Monitoring Evaluation (QAME) team was organized, which is composed of the school head, teachers, and parents, to quality assure, monitor and evaluate programs, projects and activities relative to the implementation of the BE-LCP. Moreover, the teachers held that in order to ensure successful implementation of the BE-LCP in the schools, engagement of all concerns in the educational system supported by the different stakeholders is required, for education has become a shared activity with the presence of the covid-19 pandemic.

4. Challenges Derived from the Implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP)

The perception of the elementary and secondary school of the Gamu District on the challenges derived from the implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan in the different areas are presented in the following tables.

Table 22
Perception on the Challenges in the Implementation of Curriculum and Learning Support by the Elementary and Secondary Schools

Curriculum and Learning Support Statements	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. The copy of MELCs provided by the Department of Education (DepEd) does not suit to the local context and were not fully maximized by school heads and teachers.	1.88	Challenging	1.78	Challenging
2. The MELCs per quarter are not covered by the Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) distributed by the school wherein learners are unable to cope with them.	1.89	Challenging	1.75	Challenging
3. Learners cannot cope in answering the required SLMs and Learning Activity Sheets (LAS) distributed by the school.	1.99	Challenging	1.95	Challenging
4. The school has inadequate equipment in the delivery/distribution and retrieval of modules.	1.80	Challenging	1.72	Very Challenging
Mean	1.89	Challenging	1.80	Challenging

Table 22 presents the tabulated results on the perception of the elementary and secondary schools on the challenges in the implementation of curriculum and learning support. As it is seen, the respondents perceived that this part in the implementation of the BE-LCP is challenging as supported by the general weighted mean of 1.89 in the elementary and 1.80 in the secondary.

The statement that got the least weighted mean is “The school has inadequate equipment in the delivery/distribution and retrieval of modules.” It has a weighted mean of 1.80 in the elementary and described as challenging and 1.72 in the secondary and described as very challenging.

This supports the assessment of the participants in the study of Robosa, et al. (2021) According to them the public school system, such as lack of necessary equipment, brought hardship to the school's key indicators, specifically, teachers and students. Aside from the number of students, another problem encountered by the participants was getting the trust of their students and making them realize the importance of education. Moreover, in this time of the pandemic, it is getting harder for them to facilitate the output given to their students.

Unlike the elementary schools whose learners usually come from the same barangay where the school is situated, learners in the secondary schools, according to the teachers, come from different feeder barangay of the school. This makes it difficult for the teachers since not all school have the vehicles to visit the learners in their barangays in order to distribute and retrieve their modules, answer sheets, and outputs.

Table 23

Perception on the Challenges in the Implementation of Modular Distance Learning by the Elementary And Secondary Schools

Modular Distance Learning Statements	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Teachers are unable do home visits or initiate interventions to learners needing remediation or assistance.	1.87	Challenging	1.73	Very Challenging
2. No member of the family or other stakeholders in the community serve as para-teachers to learners needing more assistance.	1.99	Challenging	1.92	Challenging
3. Learners do not manifest higher level of learning outcomes through modular learning approach.	2.04	Challenging	2.07	Challenging

4. The teachers are unable to use varied assessment strategies in the Modular Distance Learning.	1.88		1.79	
		Challenging		Challenging
Mean	1.95	Challenging	1.88	Challenging

Table 23 displays the perception on the challenges in the implementation of modular distance learning by the elementary and secondary schools. This area in the implementation of the BE-LCP was perceived as challenging based on the displayed general weighted mean of 1.95 in elementary and 1.88 in the secondary schools.

Among the four statements in this area, “Teachers are unable do home visits or initiate interventions to learners needing remediation or assistance” is the statement that got the lowest weighted mean from the two groups of respondents. It is 1.87, which is described as challenging, in the elementary, and 1.73, which is very challenging, in the secondary.

Obviously, what’s pulling the teachers, according to them, from doing home visitations to initiate interventions and remediation is the fear of getting infected by the virus or, unknowingly, they might be infecting the learners with the virus if ever they did so. Another reason is to keep the mandate of the Inter-Agency Task Force of limiting the mobility of the people in order to control the transmission of the virus.

In addition, according to Castroverde and Alcalá’s (2021) study, the common problem of teachers in monitoring students’ performance is the lack of effective communication. This is due to students’ lack of gadgets as well as unstable internet connectivity since most of the monitoring is being done through messenger and other social media platforms. Teachers’ challenges in collecting the modules are associated with students’ responsibility in complying with all the requirements specified in their activities. The failure of students to follow the set schedule for the submission of modules affects the teacher’s schedule in checking the modules as it consumes time in checking all the outputs of the students.

After collecting the modules, teachers are expected to check and evaluate students’ answers. Checking is considered as one of the essential parts of teachers’ role in monitoring the students’ performance. However, there are various issues and challenges that teachers encounter in the process of checking and evaluating students’ outputs. The teachers find it difficult to check outputs with no answers as it indicates that they have nothing to record with regards to the students’ performance. On top of that, the fact that students have no answers means that students are not interested in the process of learning. Hence, it is challenging for teachers to evaluate a student without evidence of learning.

As the teacher evaluates the performance of students, giving feedback to students is also necessary to let the students know the status of their learning through the given modules. However, it was found out that the current way of learning and giving of instruction creates a dilemma on how can teachers address students regarding their

performance. According to the respondents of the study, communication to both teachers and parents is being done through text and social media platforms such as the messenger. However, not all students have the access to these gadgets and not all of them can afford to buy a load. There are also students who are residing in areas with poor internet connection. Due to these, the teachers find it difficult to inform learners of the status of their learning as well as they find it challenging to give feedback on students' outputs.

Table 24
Perception on the Challenges in the Implementation of Capacity Building by the Elementary And Secondary Schools

Capacity Building	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Webinars for parents and stakeholders were not done to capacitate them as partners in the implementation of the BE-LCP.	1.77	Challenging	1.65	Very Challenging
2. Orientations were not done for parents and stakeholders to convey their important roles in the implementation of the BE-LCP.	1.89	Challenging	1.95	Challenging
3. Conferences were not conducted to ensure high level of awareness on the priority programs and projects as well as essential directives of DepEd in this time of health crisis.	1.82	Challenging	1.81	Challenging
Mean	1.83	Challenging	1.80	Challenging

Table 24 exhibits the perception of the respondents in the elementary and secondary schools on the challenges of capacity building as part of the implementation of the BE-LCP. It can be noticed that in this area, the respondents assessed it to be challenging as shown by its general weighted mean of 1.83 in elementary and 1.80 in secondary.

The statement that got the highest weighted mean from both group of respondents is "Orientations were not done for parents and stakeholders to convey their important roles in the implementation of the BE-LCP," and the statement that got the lowest mean, also from both group of respondents, is "Webinars for parents and stakeholders were not done to capacitate them as partners in the implementation of the BE-LCP." The latter was assessed by the elementary schools to be challenging with a weighted mean of 1.77 while the secondary schools assessed it to be very challenging with a weighted mean of 1.65.

Orientations to parents and stakeholders, according to elementary teachers, were not able to be provided at some point because of the health restrictions, such as face-to-face and large number of people gathering together were not permitted. As to the secondary school teachers, they claimed that giving of webinars to parents and stakeholders to capacitate them in the implementation of the BE-LCP was very challenging because not everyone has internet connections and the unavailability of communication gadgets such as smartphones and computers.

The study of Kentnor as cited by Palvia, et al. (2018) affirms, further, the result as they said that there are also the institutional factors as challenges such as a limited understanding about distance learning pedagogy and learning styles of the students, lack of administrative support for virtual teaching and for marketing the program, number of students enrolled, faculty qualifications, tuition rates, and length of the program. Aside from this, it was also cited that there is a reduce on the quality of education, increased training costs, faculty resistance, financial constraints, misaligned course content, increased cost of updates on technology, less teacher-student interaction, to name but a few, are some of those challenges facing distance learning.

Table 25

Perception on the Challenges in the Implementation of Requiring Health Standards to Increase Physical and Mental Resilience by the Elementary and Secondary Schools

Requiring Health Standards to Increase Physical and Mental Resilience Statements	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Personnel are not engaged in at least 30 minutes of daily physical activities to increase physical resilience.	1.86	Challenging	1.77	Challenging
2. Mental Health and Psychosocial Support and debriefing sessions to personnel, and the promotion of “work-life balance” through project scheduling activities and rotation workforce are not established.	1.94	Challenging	1.80	Challenging
Mean	1.90	Challenging	1.79	Challenging

Table 25 illustrates the perception on the challenges in the implementation of requiring health standards to increase physical and mental resilience by the elementary and secondary schools. With a general weighted mean of 1.90 in the elementary and 1.79 in secondary, this part is weighed as challenging.

Based on the assessment of the two groups of respondents, “Personnel are not engaged in at least 30 minutes of daily physical activities to increase physical resilience” is the statement that got the lowest weighted mean. The weighted mean in elementary is 1.86 and 1.77 in the secondary. Both are considered as challenging.

Engaging into physical activities such as exercise even for at least 30 minutes daily should have been beneficial as it can change how to respond to stress and boost resilience, according to the secondary school teachers. However, this had been overlooked by school administrators, as it was not proposed to the teachers for them to do. In addition, according to elementary school teachers, they said that when they arrive at school they tend to proceed directly to their work area and focus on checking learners’ outputs and doing other work-related activities without spending some time to have physical activities, either individually or in group.

Table 26

Perception on the Challenges in the Implementation of Requiring Health Standards to Reduce Transmission by the Elementary and Secondary Schools

Requiring Health Standards to Reduce Transmission Statements	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Requiring symptomatic and asymptomatic individuals to stay at home and seek medical attention and consultation are not enforced.	2.07	Challenging	1.79	Challenging
2. Access to basic hygiene facilitates and the rational use of personal protective equipment (PPEs) such as masks are not observed.	2.01	Challenging	1.77	Challenging
Mean	2.04	Challenging	1.78	Challenging

Table 26 demonstrates the challenges in the implementation of requiring health standards to reduce transmission as perceived by the elementary and secondary schools. It further demonstrates that this area in the implementation of the BE-LCP is challenging as gauged by the respondents, with a general weighted mean of 2.04 in elementary and 1.78 in secondary.

Unanimously, the statement that got the lowest weighted mean is “Access to basic hygiene facilitates and the rational use of personal protective equipment (PPEs) such as masks are not observed” as measured by the respondents. The weighted mean in elementary is 2.01 while in the secondary is 1.78; both are pronounced as challenging.

The unavailability of wash facilities outside the school buildings or at the gate, according to elementary teachers, made it susceptible to school personnel to contract the virus as they have nowhere to sanitize their hands from time to time should they go outside their respective classrooms or work areas. As to the secondary school teachers, they observed that though the personnel wear facemasks and face shields, some wear them improperly or they don't wear them at all while they are at their work places or when they are even conversing with others.

Table 27

Perception on the Challenges in the Implementation of Requiring Health Standards to Reduce Contact by the Elementary and Secondary Schools

Requiring Health Standards to Reduce Contact Statements	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. The implementation of strict physical distancing of at least one (1) meter apart in all common areas is not observed.	1.78	Challenging	1.67	Very Challenging
2. The conduct of large physical gatherings and other activities where physical distancing may not be possible is not restricted.	1.80	Challenging	1.75	Challenging
Mean	1.79	Challenging	1.71	Very Challenging

Table 27 reveals the challenges in the implementation of requiring health standards to reduce contact as perceived by the respondents from the elementary and secondary schools. The table further reveals that the respondents vary in their perception as supported by the general weighted mean wherein the elementary schools perceived this part in the implementation of the BE-LCP as challenging, while secondary schools perceived this as very challenging. The general weighted mean in elementary is 1.79 and in the secondary schools is 1.71.

With a weighted mean of 1.78 in the elementary, which is described as challenging, and with a weighted mean of 1.67 in the secondary, which is described as very challenging, the statement that got the lowest weighted mean is "The implementation of strict physical distancing of at least one (1) meter apart in all common areas is not observed."

Short conversations with co-workers had become part in the daily lives of employees. This is the very reason why they, according to secondary school teachers, tend to group together, sometimes, not minding about the required physical distance. They even

reasoned out that they, however, did not fail to wear personal protection equipment such as facemasks and face shields while having such conversations. Moreover, according to elementary school teachers, physical distancing was also challenging to observe, most especially, when there is only one common faculty room for all the teachers in the school.

Table 28

Perception on the Challenges in the Implementation of Requiring Health Standards to Reduce Duration of Infection by the Elementary and Secondary Schools

Requiring Health Standards to Reduce Duration of Infection Statements	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Identification of possible cases and daily health inspection to detect symptoms of infection is not established.	1.77	Challenging	1.68	Very Challenging
2. The school clinic is unable to ensure the provision of referral services and follow-up of status of learners, teachers, and personnel in appropriate health facilities.	1.74	Very Challenging	1.66	Very Challenging
Mean	1.76	Challenging	1.67	Very Challenging

Table 28 shows the perception by the elementary and secondary schools on the challenges in the implementation of the requiring health standards to reduce duration of infection. The perception of the two sets of respondents, again, vary in this area of the BE-LCP. The table, further, shows the elementary schools assessed this as challenging and the secondary schools assessed it as very challenging with an overall weighted mean of 1.76 and 1.67 respectively.

In this part, the statement that got the lowest weighted mean is “The school clinic is unable to ensure the provision of referral services and follow-up of status of learners, teachers, and personnel in appropriate health facilities.” Its weighted mean in the elementary is 1.74 and in the secondary schools is 1.66. Both perception is described as very challenging.

Based on the claims of some secondary school teachers, the very problem is the inexistence of a functioning clinic in some of the secondary schools and a school nurse who really stays in the school and man the clinic. As to the elementary schools, though they said that there is a district clinic and a nurse, the problem is that the nurse could not do the provision of referral services and follow-up of status of learners, teachers, and personnel in appropriate health facilities alone. Another is the distance of the district clinic, which is far, from most of the elementary schools is the area.

Table 29

Perception on the Challenges in the Implementation of Stakeholders' Engagement and Partnership by the Elementary and Secondary Schools

Stakeholders' Engagement and Partnership Statements	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Cleaning and disinfecting school buildings, classrooms, and other school facilities are not coordinated with the local government units (LGU) or other non-government organizations (NGOs) and volunteers.	1.84	Challenging	1.72	Very Challenging
2. Partnership between the school and focal persons to raise the availability of thermal scanners, sanitizing equipment and materials, cleaning tools, personal protective equipment (PPE), medicines, printing materials, and the like are not established.	1.85	Challenging	1.75	Challenging
3. The <i>Gulayan sa Tahanan</i> and Urban Vegetable Gardening at Home as Part of <i>Brigada Eskwela</i> and School-Family-Community partnerships to promote sustainable food supply at homes were not implemented.	1.83	Challenging	1.70	Very Challenging
4. <i>Brigada Pagbasa</i> in the Learning Continuity Plan was not strengthened.	1.74	Very Challenging	1.59	Very Challenging
Mean	1.82	Challenging	1.69	Very Challenging

Table 29 presents the perception on the challenges in the implementation of stakeholders' engagement and partnership by the elementary and secondary schools. The two groups of respondents have different observation to this area as shown in the table. Elementary schools regarded it as challenging, with an overall weighted mean of 1.82, while secondary schools viewed it as very challenging, with a general weighted mean of 1.69.

Among the four statements, “*Brigada Pagbasa* in the Learning Continuity Plan was not strengthened” got the least weighted mean in the elementary and secondary schools. It has 1.74 in elementary and 1.59 in secondary. Both are described as very challenging.

What was challenging, according to elementary school teachers, is the unavailability of volunteers to achieve the objectives of the activity, since their services are for free and they too are skeptic because of the health situation. Another was that since *Brigada Pagbasa* is an after-school reading program, encouraging learners to take part in it was also a challenge. Though, according to secondary school teachers, materials were provided by the schools, it was also very challenging because of the absence of internet connections as well as electronic devices in reaching out the learners due to the distance of the learners from the teacher facilitators.

Table 30

Perception on the Challenges in the Implementation of Governance and Operations by the Elementary And Secondary Schools

Governance and Operations	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Facilities and infrastructure are not improved in terms of school and classroom structuring, establishment of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene (WASH) in Schools (Wins) Facilities, and ICT and Internet connectivity.	1.70	Very Challenging	1.61	Strongly Disagree
2. There is no transparency in the utilization of funds downloaded to the school for the implementation of BE-LCP.	1.71	Very Challenging	1.76	Challenging
3. Researches are not conducted as inputs for LCP formulation and learning modalities to be implemented.	1.72	Very Challenging	1.77	Challenging
Mean	1.71	Very Challenging	1.71	Very Challenging

Table 30 illustrates the perception of the elementary and secondary schools on the challenges in the implementation of governance and operations. It, further, reflects that both groups of respondents perceived this part to be very challenging. As it is shown, the general weighted mean in the elementary and secondary schools is, identically, 1.71.

“Facilities and infrastructure are not improved in terms of school and classroom structuring, establishment of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene (WASH) in Schools (Wins)

Facilities, and ICT and Internet connectivity” got the lowest weighted mean, both in elementary and secondary schools.

With all fairness, according to the teachers from the elementary and secondary schools, there was improvement in the water, sanitation and hygiene in their respective schools. This is so because school administrators put up additional lavatory and wash areas for disinfection and sanitation. However, when it comes to ICT and Internet connectivity, DepEd, according to the teachers, failed to provide the necessary devices to be used in reaching out to the learners. DepEd presumed that each teacher already had these gadgets. With regards to Internet connectivity, teachers claimed that they have to make use of their own money in order to have data balance in their mobile phones or Internet modems to be used in online synchronous and asynchronous instructions and teaching.

Moreover, Robosa, et al. (2021) found out that most teachers are significantly challenged by lack of resources, handling of students, and the submission and workloads that contribute to stress and burnout and the occurrence of the digital age limited most public-school teachers.

According to the participants, the public school system, such as lack of necessary equipment, brought hardship to the school's key indicators, specifically, teachers and students. Moreover, in this time of the pandemic, it is getting harder for them to facilitate the output given to their students. It is not just the students but also teachers who encountered difficulties submitting paperwork and other tasks assigned to them.

Furthermore, based on Castroverde and Alcala's (2021) study, teachers encounter different challenges in the implementation of modular distance learning modality. Teachers' challenges in preparing the modules are related to the time, materials, and supplies needed to prepare and print the modules. The lack of printing materials and scarcity of supplies affect the productivity of teachers in the production of modules.

These claims are not far from the experiences of the elementary teachers as they too claimed that equipment such as printers, copiers, laptop computers and other essential gadgets for communication and reproduction of a large number of self-learning modules, learning activity sheets, and learning materials are not available or are not in good condition. No or poor internet connectivity too posed a challenge to teachers for communication and instruction.

Table 31

Perception on the Challenges in the Implementation of Advocacy and Awareness by the Elementary And Secondary Schools

Advocacy and Awareness Statements	Elementary		Secondary	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. A regular conduct of information dissemination of all related programs, projects and activities of the LCP is not sustained.	1.81	Challenging	1.74	Very Challenging
2. Linkages with radio stations are not established to disseminate relevant information.	1.79	Challenging	1.70	Very Challenging
Mean	1.80	Challenging	1.72	Very Challenging

Table 31 displays the perception on the challenges in the implementation of advocacy and awareness by the elementary and secondary schools. This area in the implementation of the BE-LCP was perceived as challenging by the elementary schools based on the overall weighted mean of 1.80 and perceived by the secondary schools as very challenging with an overall weighted mean of 1.72.

The statement “Linkages with radio stations are not established to disseminate relevant information” got the lowest weighted mean from both sets of respondents. It was assessed by the elementary schools as challenging with a weighted mean of 1.79, while secondary schools assessed it as very challenging with a weighted mean of 1.70.

The abovementioned statement found by the elementary schools to be challenging due to the reason that, according to the teachers, there were no radio stations within the municipality or nearby the municipality of Gamu with which they could easily access and collaborate. On the other hand, secondary schools found it to be very challenging because it needs shelling out some school funds to buy air time from radio stations. Anyway, according to them, there are online platforms that they could use in information dissemination and through the use of text messages using their mobile phones to reach out to the learners, parents, guardians, and other stakeholders.

Table 32

Perception on the Challenges in the Implementation of Monitoring and Evaluation by the Elementary And Secondary Schools

Monitoring and Evaluation	School Heads		Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. School issues and concerns that arise in the implementation of the BE-LCP are not elevated to the District Level for immediate action.	1.76	Challenging	1.72	Very Challenging
2. Research undertaking is not maximized as monitoring and evaluation mechanism.	1.77	Challenging	1.76	Challenging
Mean	1.77	Challenging	1.74	Very Challenging

Table 32 exhibits the perception of the respondents in the elementary and secondary schools on the challenges of monitoring and evaluation as part of the implementation of the BE-LCP. It can be noticed that in this area the elementary schools assessed it as challenging as being shown with a general weighted mean of 1.77 and very challenging in the secondary schools with a general weighted mean of 1.74.

Of the two statements in this part, it is the statement “School issues and concerns that arise in the implementation of the BE-LCP are not elevated to the District Level for immediate action” that has the least weighted mean as weighed by the elementary and secondary schools. In elementary schools, the weighted mean is 1.76, that is challenging, and in the secondary schools, the weighted mean is 1.72, which is very challenging.

On one hand, elementary school teachers believed that school administrators failed to communicate to the internal stakeholders the issues and concerns that arise in the implementation of the learning continuity plan more than elevating it to the district level. They are convinced that should issue and concerns arose, it would have been better that school heads had have them discussed among them inside the school, and have them find solutions to. On the other hand, secondary school teachers reasoned out that it was very challenging because they held that there were no functioning monitoring and evaluation team established, whose very function is to oversee the smooth implementation of the LCP, in the first place.

Tria (2020) said that despite lockdowns and community quarantines, every country wishes to maintain and provide high quality education. As a result, new normal education setups have emerged in the education sector. Under the current educational situation, the scenario presents a significant impediment to each educational leader's decision-making process. It calls for an action that would study the problems and changes that arise as a result of this pandemic to develop and design educational policies and measures ensuring

a lesser adverse impact on the education of such crises in the future. Also, understanding the issues that come along with the abrupt changes made to educational setup in responding to the emerging educational needs due to this pandemic is necessary to attain the quality of education that every student deserves. Continued review and analysis of all aspects of education and the changes made, the effects of this educational disturbance and other prevalent factors affecting the school and the students' learning are of importance.

5. Elementary and Secondary Schools' Perception with Regard to the Opportunities and Challenges Derived from the Implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP)

The perception of the elementary and secondary school teachers from the Gamu District regarding the opportunities and challenges derived from the implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan are presented in the following tables.

a. Opportunities

Table 33

Results of the Test of Significant Difference on the Opportunities in the Implementation of the BE-LCP as Perceived by the Elementary and Secondary School Teachers

Opportunities on the Implementation of the BE-LCP on the following Areas	Mean		Probability of <i>F</i>	Decision	Remarks
	Elementary School Teachers	Secondary School Teachers			
Curriculum and Learning Support	3.79	3.75	0.0177	Reject Ho	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	3.72	3.76	0.0110	Reject Ho	Significant
Capacity Building	3.75	3.74	0.0709	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Increase Physical and Mental Resilience	3.78	3.74	0.0006	Reject Ho	Significant
Reduce Transmission	3.85	3.84	0.0386	Reject Ho	Significant
Reduce Contact	3.81	3.85	0.0092	Reject Ho	Significant
Reduce Duration of Infection	3.76	3.84	0.0198	Reject Ho	Significant
Stakeholders' Engagement and Partnership	3.79	3.79	0.0887	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Governance and Operation	3.79	3.81	0.0170	Reject Ho	Significant
Advocacy and Awareness	3.80	3.86	0.0339	Reject Ho	Significant
Monitoring and Evaluation	3.81	3.79	0.1926	Accept Ho	Not Significant

The results of the test of significant difference on the opportunities in the implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) as perceived by the elementary and secondary schools are disclosed in Table 33.

It is revealed from the results that the F-probability values are less than 0.05 except for the capacity building, stakeholders' engagement and partnership, and monitoring and evaluation. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 significance level. Therefore, there is significant difference on the opportunities in the implementation of the BE-LCP as perceived by the elementary and secondary school teachers along curriculum and learning support, modular distance learning, increase physical and mental resilience, reduce transmission, reduce contact, reduce duration of infection, governance and operation, and advocacy and awareness. It shows that the two groups of teachers vary in their perceptions of the opportunities on the implementation of the BE-LCP along the aforementioned areas. It is noted further that the elementary school teachers have better perceptions on the opportunities of implementing the BE-LCP along curriculum and leaning support, increase physical and mental awareness and reduce transmission since they have the higher means. Whereas the secondary school teachers perceive better the opportunities of implementing the BE-LCP along modular distance learning, reduce contact, reduce duration of infection, governance and operation, and advocacy and awareness for they have the higher mean responses.

On the other hand, there is no significant difference on the opportunities in the implementation of BE-LCP as perceived by the elementary and secondary school teachers along capacity building, stakeholders, engagement and partnership, and monitoring and evaluation. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 significance level. It implies that the two groups of teachers do not vary in their perception on the opportunities of implementing the BE-LCP along the said three areas. It means further that the two elementary and secondary school teachers have similarities in their responses.

b. Challenges

Table 34

Results of the Test of Significant Difference on the Challenges in the Implementation of the BE-LCP as Perceived by the Elementary and Secondary School Teachers

Challenges on the Implementation of the BE-LCP on the following Areas	Mean		Probability of <i>F</i>	Decision	Remarks
	Elementary School Teachers	Secondary School Teachers			
Curriculum and Learning Support	1.89	1.80	0.0191	Reject Ho	Significant
Modular Distance Learning	1.95	1.88	0.0089	Reject Ho	Significant
Capacity Building	1.83	1.80	0.1548	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Increase Physical and Mental Resilience	1.90	1.79	0.0461	Reject Ho	Significant
Reduce Transmission	2.04	1.78	0.0335	Reject Ho	Significant
Reduce Contact	1.79	1.71	0.1665	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Reduce Duration of Infection	1.76	1.67	0.0105	Reject Ho	Significant
Stakeholders' Engagement and Partnership	1.82	1.69	0.0218	Reject Ho	Significant
Governance and Operation	1.71	1.71	0.2122	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Advocacy and Awareness	1.80	1.72	0.0368	Reject Ho	Significant
Monitoring and Evaluation	1.77	1.74	0.0343	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 34 presents the results of the test of significant difference on the challenges in the implementation of the BE-LCP as perceived by the elementary and secondary school teachers.

It is evident from the results that the probability values of *F* are less than 0.05 except for the capacity building, reduce contact, and governance and operation. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is significant difference on the challenges in the implementation of BE-LCP as perceived by the elementary and secondary school teachers along curriculum and learning support, modular distance learning, increase physical and mental resilience, reduce transmission, reduce duration of infection, stakeholders' engagement and partnership, advocacy and

awareness, and monitoring and evaluation. It shows that the two groups of teachers-respondents vary in their perceptions of the challenges met in implementing the BE-LCP along the aforementioned eight areas. It is further inferred as indicated by the mean in the table that the elementary school teachers find more somewhat challenge on their part in implementing the BE-LCP along the said eight areas for they obtain the higher mean responses than the secondary school teachers.

However, there is no significant difference on the challenges in the implementation of BE-LCP as perceived by the elementary and secondary school teachers along capacity building, reduce contact, and governance and operation. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 significance level. It implies that the two groups of teacher-respondents do not differ in their perceptions of the challenges in the implementation of BE-LCP along the said three areas. It states further that they have similar responses on the challenges of implementing the BE-LCP along these three mentioned areas.

6. School Performance

The performance of the elementary and secondary schools at the Gamu District before (School Year 2019-2020) and during (School Year 2020-2021) the implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan are presented in the following tables.

Table 35
Performance of Elementary Schools

No.	Indicators		SY 2019-2020	SY 2020-2021
1.	Enrolment Rate		98.23	102.61
2.	Dropout Rate		0.04	0
3.	Participation Rate		99.73	99.77
4.	Completion Rate		99.27	98.51
5.	Exit Assessment	Numeracy Rate	96.75	95.81
		Literacy Rate	93.11	91.98

Table 35 presents the performance of elementary schools in the District of Gamu in the different indicators before and during the implementation of the BE-LCP. As the table shows, significant changes took place during the implementation of the BE-LCP. On one hand, elementary schools' enrolment rate went up from 98.23 to 102.61, dropout rate dropped from 0.04 to 0, and participation rate slightly ascended from 99.73 to 99.77. On the other hand, completion rate, numeracy rate, and literacy rate went down from 99.27 to 98.51, 96.75 to 95.81, and 93.11 to 91.98 respectively.

With the rise in enrolment, the result affirms what the U.S. Department of Education (2010) revealed on the effectiveness of distance education for the students. In this time of health emergency brought about by the covid-19 pandemic, continuity of education is considered still of high importance.

Based on the observation of the elementary teachers, they said that some of the reasons that gave rise to enrolment were the transfer of learners from private schools that

were affected by the pandemic to public schools. Another reason is that there were learners who decided to return to school after dropping out for a while since the learning modality that were employed by the elementary schools in the new normal is modular distance learning. Consequently, due to the learning modality that was employed, it resulted to no drop out since, according to them, the learners do not need to go to school anymore, instead they are studying at the comfort of their homes.

When it comes to class instruction and learners' assessment, the results affirm Canonizado's (2020) claim that teachers face difficulties under the current normal education system. These problems include teaching the learners where it is difficult for teachers to reach out all the learners at home, even if the teachers are using different forms of communication. Because the virus is highly contagious, contact between the teachers and learners had been reduced. It is therefore quite difficult for them to develop skills of the learners because the learners remain at home while learning the lessons. Not all parents have the desire and ability to support their children in their studies. Some parents lack the ability to comprehend the handwritten details written on the modules.

The common problem of teachers in monitoring students' performance according to Castroverde and Alcala (2021) is the lack of effective communication. This is due to students' lack of gadgets as well as unstable internet connectivity since most of the monitoring is being done through messenger and other social media platforms. Teachers' challenges in collecting the modules are associated with students' responsibility in complying with all the requirements specified in their activities. The failure of students to follow the set schedule for the submission of modules affects the teacher's schedule in checking the modules as it consumes time in checking all the outputs of the students.

After collecting the modules, teachers are expected to check and evaluate students' answers. Checking is considered as one of the essential parts of teachers' role in monitoring the students' performance. However, there are various issues and challenges that teachers encounter in the process of checking and evaluating students' outputs. The teachers find it difficult to check outputs with no answers as it indicates that they have nothing to record with regards to the students' performance. On top of that, the fact that students have no answers means that students are not interested in the process of learning. Hence, it is challenging for teachers to evaluate a student without evidence of learning.

As the teacher evaluates the performance of students, giving feedback to students is also necessary to let the students know the status of their learning through the given modules. However, it was found out that the current way of learning and giving of instruction creates a dilemma on how can teachers address students regarding their performance. According to the respondents of the study, communication to both teachers and parents is being done through text and social media platforms such as the messenger. However, not all students have the access to these gadgets and not all of them can afford to buy a load. There are also students who are residing in areas with poor internet connection. Due to these, the teachers find it difficult to inform learners of the

status of their learning as well as they find it challenging to give feedback on students' outputs.

Table 36
Performance of Secondary Schools

No.	Indicators	SY 2019-2020	SY 2020-2021
1.	Enrolment Rate	102.31	106.86
2.	Dropout Rate	1.61	0.72
3.	Participation Rate	96.99	100
4.	Completion Rate	97.67	99.78
5.	Exit Assessment	Numeracy Rate	98.83
		Literacy Rate	99.05
			99.38

Table 36 shows the performance of secondary schools in the different indicators before and during the implementation of the BE-LCP. Its implementation made a positive impact to the secondary schools as the table reveals. Enrolment rate went up from 102.31 to 106.86 and, subsequently, dropout rate went down from 1.61 to 0,72. Another notable development that took place were the changes in participation rate as it moved up from 96.99 to 100 and completion rate from 97.67 to 99.78. Numeracy rate progressed from 98.83 to 99.1 and literacy rate as well developed from 99.05 to 99.38.

The observation of the secondary school teachers shows similarity with that of the elementary school teachers in the rise of enrolment and in the decrease of dropout rate. According to them, enrolment increased due to the transfer of learners as well as the number of learners who stopped from studying and went back to school since the learning modality that secondary school chose was modular distance learning.

With every positive note that took place in the secondary schools amidst the covid-19 pandemic, the outcomes affirm the kind of education that DepEd Secretary Leonor M. Briones wants. As cited by Batalon, et al. (2020) she is hopeful to further transform Philippine education in response to the changing world with the drastic changes in education brought by the pandemic. "Education is not going to be the same as education during my time or during your time it's going to change, and the change has already started. We already recognize the signals; we see the increased role of technology and science. "We see the need to encourage not only our teachers but our learners to not only specialize and memorize; but to know many things, to know how to analyze, to know how to be objective, to know how to come to break a problem apart and come up with a solution. *Ito ang klase ng edukasyon na gusto natin!* (This is the kind of education that we want),".

7. Implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) and Its Effect to School Performance

The effect of the Implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) in the performance of the elementary and secondary schools at the Gamu District are presented in the following tables.

Table 37
Effect of BE-LCP to the Performance of Elementary Schools

No.	Indicators	SY 2019-2020	SY 2020-2021	Rate of Increase	Rate of Decrease	Remarks	
1.	Enrolment Rate	98.23	102.61	4.46%	-	Marginal	
2.	Dropout Rate	0.04	0	-	100%	High	
3.	Participation Rate	99.73	99.77	0.04%	-	Marginal	
4.	Completion Rate	99.27	98.51	-	0.76%	Marginal	
5.	Exit Assessment	Numeracy Rate	96.75	95.81	-	0.97%	Marginal
		Literacy Rate	93.11	91.98	-	1.21%	Marginal

Table 37 illustrates the effect of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) to the performance of elementary schools. In its implementation, enrolment rate had a 4.46 percent increase and participation rate had an increase of 0.04 percent; both are interpreted as marginal. It is good to note dropout rate having 100 percent decrease during the implementation of the BE-LCP, and this positive development is interpreted as high. However, completion, numeracy, and literacy rates decreased. As to completion rate, it decreased to 0.76 percent, numeracy rate reduced to 0.97 percent, and literacy rate lessened to 1.21 percent. These are interpreted as marginal.

Table 38
Effect of BE-LCP to the Performance of Secondary Schools

Indicators		SY 2019-2020	SY 2020-2021	Rate of Increase	Rate of Decrease	Remarks
1. Enrolment Rate		102.31	106.86	4.45%	-	Marginal
2. Dropout Rate		1.61	0.72	-	55.27%	Average
3. Participation Rate		96.99	100	3.10%	-	Marginal
4. Completion Rate		97.67	99.78	2.16%	-	Marginal
5.Exit Assessment	Numeracy Rate	98.83	99.1	0.27%	-	Marginal
	Literacy Rate	99.05	99.38	0.33%	-	Marginal

Table 38 exposes the effect of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) to the performance of secondary schools. The implementation of the BE-LCP had a positive impact as shown in the different indicators as far as the secondary school are concerned. As the table shows, dropout rate decreased and the rest of the indicators increased. Dropout rate decreased to 55.27 percent and is interpreted as average. Furthermore, enrolment rate had an increase of 4.45 percent, participation rate with 3.10 percent, completion rate with 2.16 increase, literacy rate had an increase of 0.27 percent, and literacy rate with an increase of 0.33 percent. These are interpreted as marginal.

Conclusions

The Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) was fully implemented in Gamu District.

All the areas in the implementation of the BE-LCP were considered as opportunities as perceived by the elementary and secondary school teachers in the district. Although this is true, the same areas were also seen as challenging and very challenging by the elementary and secondary school teachers in the implementation of the BE-LCP. Except governance and operations, which was determined as very challenging, the rest were assessed as challenging by the elementary school teachers. On the part of the secondary school teachers, some areas were gauged as challenging such as curriculum and learning support, modular distance learning, capacity building, requiring health standards to increase physical and mental resilience, and requiring health standards to reduce transmission. While requiring health standards to reduce contact, requiring health standards to reduce duration of infection, stakeholders' engagement and partnership, governance and operations, advocacy and awareness, and monitoring and evaluation were weighed as very challenging.

Based on the findings, the BE-LCP implementation played a significant role in fulfilling the mandate of the Department of Education which is to continue providing quality education to Filipinos despite a crisis as shown in the rise in the number of learners who enrolled, in the increase of participation rate, as well as the decrease in the number of learners who dropped out, both in the elementary and secondary schools. Although completion rate and exit assessments went down in the elementary schools, a complete different picture is shown in the part of the secondary schools since the said indicators rose. These changes in the numbers, however, have marginal effect to the performance of the elementary and secondary schools in the District of Gamu. Only in the decrease of dropout rate had a high and average impact to the performance of the elementary and secondary schools respectively.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are hereby presented:

1. The extent of the implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan in the District of Gamu promotes positive outcomes. Thus, the BE-LCP should be intensified, sustained and maintained by the schools with the support of the teachers, staff and other stakeholders, and work on the area that post challenges.
2. In view of the upskilling and reskilling of teachers, school leaders should focus on professional development for teachers and provide technical assistance to them, so that they will continue to gain knowledge and competencies in order for them to perform their function effectively and efficiently both in the distance and in-person learning process.
3. Schools should continue to practice the DepEd required health standards to ensure the protection of the health, safety and well-being of learners, teachers and personnel, and prevent further transmission of covid-19, and when such similar case may arise in the future.
4. Teachers and school leaders should maintain a good rapport with parents and other stakeholders through giving of feedbacks and suggestions to further improve the schools performance in times such as the covid-19 pandemic as this may help both sides to provide an immediate intervention if issues and problems arise.
5. School leaders and teachers may devise a scheme for monitoring quality assurance to satisfy standard needs and requirements to ensure continued success and quality on implementing the BE-LCP.
6. Similar study maybe conducted with the inclusion of learners and parents to assess the implementation of the BE-LCP, a bigger sample size, and more school samples.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher made sure that during the conduct of the study, the following ethical concerns were followed to necessitate safe, anti-fraud, deliberate, and careful undertakings in the study:

1. The researcher, through proper communications, asked permission from the Division Office, and other concerned offices for the study;
2. The researcher also acknowledged the Department of Education and the Schools Division of Isabela for allowing her to conduct the study;
3. The researcher informed the respondents of the study through letters and a short orientation to the study. Data and information gathered were treated with utmost respect and confidentiality;
4. The researcher, properly cited gathered information and other relevant studies from authors, books, or any publications through proper citation.

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